

The effect of vent burst pressure on a vented hydrogen–air deflagration in a 1 m³ vessel

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Abstract: A series of experiments are conducted to investigate the effect of vent burst pressure on stoichiometric hydrogen–air premixed flame propagation and pressure history in a 1 m³ rectangular vessel in this paper. Pressure buildup and flame evolution are recorded using piezoelectric pressure transducers and a high-speed camera, respectively. The results show typical pressure peaks of three different mechanisms for all vent burst pressures in the experiments. The first pressure peak, generated by the rupture of the vent cover, increases with the vent failure pressure, with the subsequent outflow inertia of combustion products giving rise to a negative pressure. The second pressure peak results from the constant bulk motion of the flame bubble (the Helmholtz oscillation), and the third is produced by the interaction between the combustion waves and the acoustic waves. The time interval between the first pressure peak and the second pressure transient remained nearly constant. The Helmholtz oscillation always appears as the vent ruptures and its magnitude increases with the vent burst pressure. Furthermore, the lower the vent failure pressure, the longer the Helmholtz oscillation is sustained. The peak of the acoustically enhanced pressure always occurs within several milliseconds of the flame front touching the vessel. From a theoretical perspective, Rasbash's equation models the relationship between the maximum reduced explosion overpressure and the vent burst pressure precisely. Also, it is observed that the maximum lengths of the external flames were found to be nearly identical in all tests, but the average propagation rate of the flame front increases with the vent burst pressure. It is interesting that a phenomenon of intense oscillation of internal flame bubble was observed with the increase of vent burst pressure.

Keywords: Hydrogen; Overpressure; Vented explosion; Helmholtz oscillation; Hydrogen safety

1. Introduction

With the growing interest in new energy resources, hydrogen, as one of the clean energy carriers, is widely considered an ideal substitute for fossil fuels and, thus, a means of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Hydrogen has several unique physicochemical properties, including a wide flammable concentration regime, fast burning rate, high diffusivity, and low ignition energy. The safe production, transportation, and storage of hydrogen in industry have become an important topic worldwide. Explosion venting is currently the most common method used to mitigate damage to equipment and harm to personnel as a result of an accidental explosion in process industries. A critical aspect of an explosion venting design is determining suitable venting parameters to guarantee that the venting rate of hot combustion products is sufficiently faster than their production rate, thus ensuring effective pressure relief.

Considering it as one of the more important venting parameters, most previous studies have made great contribution to study the effect of vent burst pressure on pressure development and flame propagation in hydrocarbon–air mixtures [1–13]. For instance, McCann et al. [1] conducted experiments using a methane–air mixture in two kinds of vessels, with side lengths of 18 cm and 30 cm, respectively. Two characteristic pressure transients were identified as the vent failure pressure exceeded a critical value. In addition, they found that the time interval between the two pressure transients decreased as the vent failure pressure increased. Kasmani et al. [2,3] investigated explosion venting using propane–air and methane–air mixtures with equivalence ratios ranging from 0.8 to 1.6 in a 0.2 m³ cylindrical vessel. Their findings showed that the maximum pressure does not increase monotonically with the vent failure pressure under central and rear ignition. The same vessel was employed by Fakandu et al. [4] to investigate the effect of vent burst pressure on the maximum reduced explosion

pressure of methane–air and ethylene–air mixtures. They observed that the dominant peak pressure depends on both the vent burst pressure and the vent coefficient K ($K = V^{2/3}/A_v$, where V is the vessel volume and A_v is the vent area). Similar results were found by Chow et al. [5] and Zhen et al. [6] using methane–air mixture in a 0.056 m³ cylindrical vessel and two spherical vessels of 22L and 110L, respectively. Molkov [7] pointed out that the maximum pressure increases with the vent burst pressure, P_v , when P_v is less than 200 kPa, but decreases when P_v is greater than 200 kPa. In contrast, Ponizy and Leyer [8] identified a monotonic increase in peak pressure with vent burst pressure. DeGood et al. [9] employed a 2.3 m³ cylindrical vessel to investigate vented explosions using a propane (5%)–air (95%) mixture. They found that, in addition to the vent burst pressure, the maximum pressure is determined by the ignition location, discharge duct, and obstacles. Cooper et al. [10] used three cubic and near-cubic vessels (a 0.76 m³ volume cube, a 2.55 m³ volume cube, and a 2.41 m³ volume cuboid) to carry out experiments with a mixture containing 10% natural gas. They recorded four pressure peaks. In particular, they found that two pressure peaks become dominant as the vent failure pressure increases, the first generated by an external explosion and the second by a flame acoustic interaction. In recent studies, Bao et al. [11] investigated the effect of vent failure pressure on a vented explosion pressure profile in a 12 m³ chamber. They also found four pressure peaks that depend on initial conditions other than the vent burst pressure, with two dominant pressure transients: the first generated by the rupture of the vent cover, and the second produced by acoustically driven combustion. Guo et al. [12] conducted experiments on venting explosion using methane-air mixtures in a 0.012 m³ cylindrical vessel. They concluded that the maximum overpressure in vessel and maximum length of the external flame increase with the vent burst pressure. Cao et al. [13] performed experiments on vented explosion using ethylene-air mixtures in a 2m × 1.1m × 0.5m cylindrical vessel.

As the vent burst pressure increases, the same trend that internal peak pressure is increasing accordingly was found.

Despite many experiments have been implemented on vented explosions, it is necessary to investigate explosion venting of hydrogen–air mixtures for its faster burning rates and higher diffusivity than that of hydrocarbon–air mixtures. Therefore, it may be dangerous to apply the findings related to hydrocarbon–air mixtures to hydrogen–air mixtures, which have not been studied sufficiently [14–18]. A 2.3 m diameter spherical vessel was used by Kumar et al. [14] to study 6–20 vol. % hydrogen explosion venting. They concluded that the generation of maximum overpressure was influenced not only by the vent burst pressures, but by the ignition locations as well. Kasmani [15] performed explosion venting using a hydrogen–air mixture with different vent burst pressures and ignition positions in a cylindrical vessel. In this case, the maximum pressures were observed to be nearly identical for low vent burst pressures ($P_v = 9.8, 17.8, 20.9$ kPa). However, when $P_v > 42.4$ kPa and the fuel is ignited centrally, the maximum pressure decreases. Guo et al. [16] conducted experiments on venting explosions using a hydrogen–air mixture with an equivalence ratio of 2 in a 0.012 m³ cylindrical vessel with a large vent coefficient, K. They observed four pressure peaks at the vessel exit and a single pressure peak inside the vessel. Their results showed that the latter increased with the vent burst pressure and that the external flame length is not sensitive to the vent burst pressure. The same vessel was utilized by Cao et al. [17] to study the effect of vent burst pressure on the external explosion. A similar relationship between internal peak pressure and vent burst pressure was found, however, external peak pressure is not only sensitive to the vent burst pressure but ignition locations. Experiments on the vented explosion of hydrogen-air mixtures from a 150-cm-long duct to the aforementioned 0.012 m³ cylindrical vessel with a vent at the center of its side wall were conducted by

Li et al. [18]. The results illustrated that both of the overpressures, one in duct and the other in vessel, increased with the vent burst pressure.

However, these results do not seem to follow the findings for hydrocarbon–air mixtures. In addition to the aforementioned studies, several works have focused on the effect of vent burst pressure on explosion venting for hydrogen–air mixtures. Nevertheless, further research is necessary to investigate how the pressure changes for lower vent burst pressures ($P_v < 10$ kPa) and a lower vent coefficient (K), as well as the flame behavior inside and outside a vessel during a vented explosion.

This study investigates explosion venting using stoichiometric hydrogen–air mixtures in a 1 m³ rectangular vessel with a large vent area for different vent failure pressures. The study has two main objectives. First, it examines the mechanisms that generate the pressure peaks and the effect of vent failure pressure on pressure time histories. Then, the performance of equations that predict the maximum reduced explosion pressure is evaluated. Second, the current study also identifies the correlation between the pressure profile and the flame evolution inside the vessel, and the flame behavior outside the vessel.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Apparatus and equipment

The experiments on vented explosions of stoichiometric hydrogen–air mixture are conducted in a 3 cm thick stainless vessel that is 1 m wide, 0.55 m deep, and 1.8 m high (see Fig. 1). Three windows of the same size (700 mm wide, 40 mm thick, and 400 mm high) are mounted on the front face, allowing the recording of the external deflagration. A 700 mm × 400 mm vent is fitted on the top face of the vessel. Various thicknesses of paper, clamped tightly by a steel flange, are used as vent covers, corresponding to different activation pressures.

The hydrogen–air mixture is ignited by electrodes 15 cm long with an ignition energy of 500 mJ. The electrodes are located at the centerline of the back wall, 10 cm from the vent. A high-speed camera (1000 fps) is employed to record the flame inside and outside the vessel. Three piezoelectric pressure transducers (PCB 102B16) are used to record the pressure time history in the vessel during explosion venting, and are installed in the centerline of the right wall at different heights (10, 90, 170 cm) from the floor. They are further coated with a thin layer of silicon grease to eliminate thermal effects.

Figure. 1 - Layout of experiment

2.2. Operating procedure

Prior to each test, a vacuum pump is used to empty the vessel. Then, hydrogen with a concentration of 30 vol.%, calculated using Dalton's law of partial pressure, and air are pumped into the explosion enclosure up to the ambient pressure. Next, the vent is sealed using paper of different thicknesses (δ) before ignition. The flammable mixture is then ignited by the electrodes using a transistor-transistor logic (TTL) signal and, at the same time, the high-speed camera and oscillograph are triggered by a signal synchronizer to record the flame images and pressure data, respectively. In all tests, the initial temperature and pressure is maintained at 285 K and 100 kPa.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Pressure profiles

Three typical pressure curves, monitored by three pressure transducers, share a similar trend over time, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (a cutoff frequency of 200 Hz is used to clearly distinguish pressure transients). Three pressure transients of different types are always recorded in each test under the aforementioned experimental conditions. The behavior of this multi-peak pressure history and corresponding mechanisms have been reported by McCann et al. [1] and Cooper et al. [7]

Figure. 2 - Pressure histories in vessel for $\delta = 0.496\text{mm}$

According to previous investigations, the first pressure peak is generated by the rupture of the vent cover [9,19,20]. Because the oscillograph and high-speed camera are triggered simultaneously, the time of the vent failure can be determined by the time when the flame vents outside the vessel. However, Fig. 2 shows that the pressures measured by PT2 and PT3 are still increasing for a few milliseconds after the vent burst because the flame area is still increasing. In other words, the production rate of burnt gases is larger than the venting rate and, thus, the first peak pressure recorded by PT3 is always larger than that recorded by PT1 for various vent burst pressures. The pressure measured by PT1 at the time of the vent failure can be regarded as the vent burst pressure because the distance between the top pressure transducer and the vent cover is smaller than that of the two adjacent pressure transducers. The results show vent burst pressures of $P_v = 3.2, 4.9, 6.4, 18.6, 22.2,$ and 27.8 kPa corresponding to various paper thicknesses from $\delta = 0.124$ to 0.744 mm.

After the vent failure, hot burnt products are discharged immediately and the induced outflow (i.e., the discontinuity) stretches the flame bubble to the vent. Subsequently, a negative pressure occurs due to the outflow inertia. Following this negative pressure, the internal pressure oscillates around atmospheric pressure with decreasing amplitude and a frequency of 50–110 Hz. According to related literatures, these pressure oscillations result from the bulk motion of the flame bubble in the vessel, and share the same frequency as the vibration of the flame surface. This is called the Helmholtz oscillation [21–23]. With the additional reaction inside the vessel, a high-frequency, oscillatory pressure transient is generated, which is a phenomenon unique to explosion venting in large vessels [24]. This peak is produced by the interaction between the pressure waves from the combustion and acoustic modes of the vessel, called the acoustically enhanced pressure [1, 4, 9, 10, 25–31]. Because the pressure transients following the first pressure peak are generated by the Helmholtz oscillation, the largest of them (always P₂) and subsequent acoustically enhanced pressure are denoted as P_{hel} and P_{acc}, respectively, for simplification (see Fig. 2(b)).

Figure. 3 - Pressure profiles measured by PT3 under different vent burst pressures

Fig. 3 shows the internal pressure profiles recorded by PT3 for various vent burst pressures. The maximum rate of the increase in the explosion pressure $(\frac{dP}{dt})_{max}$ increases with the vent burst

pressure before the vent failure. This is the result of a chain reaction mechanism of the hydrogen and a positive feedback mechanism, in which the high pressure and temperature generated by the combustion enhance the reaction rate of the hydrogen [32], as shown in Fig. 4(a). Therefore, Fig. 3(a) shows that the pressure profile becomes steeper as the vent burst pressure increases before the first pressure peak, P_1 .

Figure. 4 - Maximum rate of explosion pressure rise and Helmholtz oscillation frequency vs. vent burst pressure (a). Time intervals among two adjacent pressure transients vs. vent burst pressure (b).

After the first pressure peak P_1 being appeared, the generation of the subsequent pressure transients is governed by two processes: the venting process of hot products, which decreases the internal pressure; and the residual combustion process inside the vessel, which increases the internal pressure [10]. A lower vent burst pressure means less fuel is consumed before the vent failure, and less fuel is expelled outside the vessel owing to the inertia of the venting process after the vent failure. As a result, more unburnt gas is left in the vessel, and the flame front expands toward the bottom of vessel after the vent burst at a lower average velocity. This leads to a longer reaction time and more pressure transients being produced, as shown in Fig. 3(b). In other words, the Helmholtz oscillation attenuates with the increase of the vent burst pressure. Therefore, Fig. 4(b) shows that the time interval between P_{hel} and P_{acc} decreases as the vent burst pressure increases. A higher vent burst pressure results in a higher

overpressure and a larger negative pressure being generated before and after the vent failure, respectively, corresponding to higher venting and backflow rates being generated as well. This is the reason why the frequency of the Helmholtz oscillation increases with the vent burst pressure, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). It is also why the time intervals between P_1 and P_{hel} are nearly identical under various vent burst pressures, as shown in Fig. 4(b). At the same time, Fig. 5 presents that the increase in the vent burst pressure results in the magnitude of the peak pressure of the Helmholtz oscillation increasing monotonically. However, no similar trend is found in the magnitude of P_{acc} .

3.2 Maximum reduced overpressure

Fig. 5 shows the correlations between the significant pressure peak and the vent burst pressure. As shown, the magnitudes of P_{hel} and P_{neg} vary with the vent burst pressure consistently in the case of high vent burst pressures, and are even roughly identical for the low vent burst pressures. This is because the amplitude of P_{hel} is dependent on the velocity of the flame front propagating downward through the vessel, and the greater products of the combustion generated before the vent rupture and the higher negative pressure P_{neg} formed in the vessel after the vent failure lead to a larger backflow rate. Thus, P_1 , P_{neg} , and P_{hel} increase monotonically with the vent burst pressure.

Figure. 5 - Characteristic overpressure vs. vent burst pressure

Fig. 3(b) and Fig. 5 show that for $\delta = 0.124$ mm and $\delta = 0.372$ mm, the acoustically enhanced

pressure becomes the dominant peak. However, there is no apparent relationship between P_{acc} and the vent burst pressure owing to the magnitude of the acoustically enhanced pressure depending on many factors, including the gas concentration, vent coefficient, size and activation pressure of the vent cover, and shape, volume, and smoothness of the vessel, among others. Until now, very few theoretical or empirical formulae have been proposed to predict its value.

Owing to the limitation of the vent burst pressure of $P_v > 10$ kPa, widely used venting design standards EN14994 [33] and NFPA68 [34] cannot be used here to predict the maximum reduced explosion pressure. Bradley and Mitcheson [35, 36] proposed equation (1), based on numerical solutions of their model and experiments with hydrocarbon–air and hydrogen–air mixtures:

$$P_{red} = 4.8 P_{stat}^{0.375} \left(\frac{A}{S_0}\right)^{-1.25}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{A} is the ratio of the vent area to the total surface area of the vessel, and S_0 is the ratio of the gas velocity ahead the initial flame front to the acoustic velocity of the unburnt gas. Rasbash [37, 38] concludes the maximum reduced explosion overpressure has a linear relationship with the vent burst pressure as in equation (2).

$$P_{red} = 1.5 P_{stat} + 0.5K. \quad (2)$$

Fig. 6 shows the results computed using the above equations and the experimental data.

Figure. 6 - Comparison of the computed and tested values of overpressure

Fig. 6 shows that for low vent burst pressures, equation (1) provides reliable predictive results for P_{red} , which is also predicted well by equation (2) in all cases examined here.

3.3 Flame behavior inside the vessel

Typical internal flame photos corresponding to different pressure peaks for the cases of $\delta = 0.248$ mm ($P_v = 4.9$ kPa) and $\delta = 0.496$ mm ($P_v = 18.6$ kPa) are shown in **Fig. 7**. The figure clearly implies that the outflow inertia of the combustion gases and the subsequent Helmholtz oscillation phenomenon, bulk motion of the flame bubble result from the negative pressure. **Fig. 7** clearly suggests that as the vent burst pressure increases, the outflow inertia becomes more intense and a greater amount of the combustion products are sucked because of the negative pressure inside the vessel. This causes the flame front to become more wrinkled, even causing a central spike, accessing the core of the burnt gases and breaking up the flame front when $P_v \geq 18.6$ kPa. At the same time, the increase in the vent burst pressure makes the bulk motion of the flame bubble become so apparent that the appearance of the first positive and negative pressure peaks of the Helmholtz oscillation produced by the equilibrium between the residual combustion and venting process can be observed even with the naked eye in the flame images. The positive pressure peak appears when the flame front and the flame bubble expand toward the bottom until they reach a maximum length. Then, the negative pressure peak is generated when the flame bubble vents outside, and the flame front begins to propagate downward again.

Figure. 7 - Flame propagation images inside vessel after ignition for $\delta = 0.248\text{mm}$ (a) and $\delta = 0.496\text{mm}$ (b).

Interestingly, the peak of the acoustically enhanced pressure always occurs within a few milliseconds of the flame front touching the bottom of the vessel, regardless of the vent burst pressure.

Fig. 8 presents the corresponding flame front location and propagation rate for $\delta = 0.248\text{ mm}$ and $\delta = 0.496\text{ mm}$. Both flame fronts expand at nearly the same speed of 8–20 m/s in the early stage of the deflagration, which is larger than the value of the laminar flame velocity because of the resulting turbulence and instability [23, 29, 39]. As discussed above, for $\delta = 0.496\text{ mm}$, the higher average reaction rate causes a higher internal pressure before the vent failure. Then, a larger backflow is generated by stronger inertia of venting process after the vent burst, which means the flame front takes less time to reach the bottom of the vessel. The larger magnitudes of the positive and negative flame speed oscillations reflect the more intense bulk motion of the flame bubble for $\delta = 0.496\text{ mm}$. However, for $\delta = 0.248\text{ mm}$, the higher frequencies and longer oscillation times of the positive and negative flame speeds are mainly responsible for generating the additional pressure transients and a longer reaction time, where the oscillation begins to decay with the flame front touching the floor of

the vessel.

Figure. 8 - Flame displacement and average velocity vs. time

3.4. Flame behavior outside the vessel

Fig. 9 shows typical flame propagation images outside the vessel for $\delta = 0.496\text{ mm}$. Hot burnt products are discharged from the vessel as soon as a vent burst occurs, causing a large fireball near the vent. On account of the top ignition, the flame front has touched the vent cover by the time the vent rupture occurs. As a result, only a small amount of unburnt gases for low vent failure pressures and none of the fuel for high vent burst pressures are expelled from the vessel prior to the arrival of the flame front after a vent failure [40]. Thus, there are no external explosions, and the fireball is caused by the expansion of burnt products. Then, the roughly spherical external expansion flame was developed to a cone-shaped flame, reaching its maximum length within tens of milliseconds. Finally, the flame length begins to decrease.

Figure. 9 - Flame propagation photographs outside vessel for $\delta = 0.496\text{mm}$. The time marked in

figure is millisecond after vent failure

Fig. 10 shows the displacement of the flame front and as function as time for various vent burst pressures. Although there is little difference in the maximum flame length, the time the flame front takes to expand to its maximum length decreases with the vent burst pressure. That is, the average flame propagation rate opposite the vent increases with the vent burst pressure, because it has a positive relation with the production rate of hot gases inside the vessel, which increases with the vent burst pressure.

Figure. 10 - Location of flame front vs. time

3. Conclusion

This study investigates the effect of vent burst pressure on flame propagation and on the buildup of pressure in a vented explosion of a stoichiometric hydrogen–air mixture. The major findings are as follows.

All tests show three positive pressure peaks and a clear negative pressure. The first pressure peak is caused by the vent burst, and the second by the inertia of venting process. The magnitudes of these two pressure peaks and the maximum rate of the increase in the explosion pressure $(\frac{dP}{dt})_{max}$ increase with the vent burst pressure.

Internal deflagration images show that the bulk motion of the flame bubble, initiated from the negative pressure, and the production and venting rates of hot products change in an inverse relationship. This leads to the formation of the next positive pressure peak, which is a Helmholtz oscillation type peak. The Helmholtz oscillation always appears at the moment of the vent failure. Then, acoustically enhanced pressure occurs due to the interaction between the combustion waves and the pressure waves. The peak of the acoustically enhanced pressure occurs within a few milliseconds of the lower flame surface touching the vessel completely. The time interval between P_1 and P_{hel} remains almost constant, whereas the time interval between P_{hel} and P_{acc} increases with the vent burst pressure.

Bradley and Mitcheson's equation exhibits good predictive ability for low vent burst pressures only, whereas Rasbash's equation predicts the maximum reduced pressure well in all of the experiments.

With an increase in the vent burst pressure, the inertia of venting process and the bulk motion become more intense. Lastly, while the maximum length of the external flame is not sensitive to the vent burst pressure, the average flame propagation rate increases with the vent burst pressure.

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